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SMEs Introducing Business Process Innovations in Italian Regions

Increased by an average of 52.73% between 2018 and 2023

Eurostat calculates the SMEs that introduce business process innovations in Italian regions. This variable is defined by a ratio. The numerator is the number of small and medium-sized enterprises that have introduced at least one business process innovation that is new to the firm or the market. The denominator is the total number of small and medium-sized enterprises. This variable captures business innovations other than product innovations. Many companies innovate by improving their business processes rather than new products. Business process innovations include process, marketing, and organizational innovations.

SMEs Introducing Business Process Innovations in 2023. Innovation in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) is a crucial driver for economic growth and technological progress. Examining the 2023 data on the number of business process innovations introduced by SMEs in various Italian regions reveals notable regional differences reflecting the diverse innovative capacity of the country. These data are essential for understanding how various regional factors directly influence the innovative activity of companies. Starting with the regions that recorded the highest number of innovations: Veneto, Lombardy, and Emilia Romagna. Veneto, leading with 211.64 innovations, highlights a dynamic and well-supported ecosystem where synergies between universities, research centers, and the industrial sector are particularly robust. Lombardy follows with 207.02 innovations, demonstrating its position as the economic and innovative heart of Italy, with a high concentration of technological industries and a favorable environment for adopting new technologies. Emilia Romagna, with 205.26 innovations, is known for its strong engineering tradition and the presence of highly specialized industrial districts, promoting continuous innovation and the evolution of production processes. Regions like Friuli Venezia Giulia and Tuscany also show high performance, with 199.63 and 191.71 innovations, respectively. These data reflect a regional environment that actively supports innovation, with policies facilitating investment in new technologies and forming strategic partnerships between the private sector and academia. Piedmont, with 190.74 innovations, underscores the importance of the automotive and robotics sectors in its innovation strategies, being home to some of the leading companies and research institutes in the sector. However, not all regions show the same level of innovative activity. Molise and Sicily, with 97.14 and 105.72 innovations respectively, highlight the challenges that less productive regions face in attracting investments and skills necessary to stimulate innovation. These numbers could indicate a lack of infrastructure

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supporting innovation, such as the availability of venture capital, as well as lesser interaction between the entrepreneurial fabric and research centers or universities. These regional disparities raise important questions about the effectiveness of development and innovation support policies. It is evident that regions like Veneto and Lombardy benefit from a virtuous circle where innovation generates further innovation, attracting investments and talents. Conversely, regions like Molise require a more targeted approach to overcome structural and cultural barriers to innovation. Regional policies should therefore be designed not only to stimulate innovation where it already thrives but also to bridge existing gaps. This could include allocating specific funds for innovation in less active regions, creating incentives for innovative startups, and developing training programs aimed at improving the digital and technological skills of SMEs. Additionally, strengthening collaborations between universities and industry in these regions could help translate academic research into concrete commercial applications, thus stimulating innovation locally. In conclusion, while some Italian regions demonstrate a high level of innovation, others lag significantly behind, highlighting the need for a more balanced and inclusive strategy. Addressing these challenges will require a joint commitment from the government, industry, and academic institutions, with the goal of creating an environment that not only values but also catalyzes innovation in all its forms. Only in this way can Italy ensure that all its regions are able to fully contribute to and benefit from the global innovation economy.

SMEs Introducing Business Process Innovations between 2018 and 2023. The landscape of innovation in Italian small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) has shown significant variation from 2018 to 2023, with notable differences between regions in terms of adopting new business processes. An analysis of the data highlights regional trends that may reflect different economic policies, levels of business support, and access to resources and funding for innovation. The region that stands out for the most marked growth both in absolute and percentage terms is Emilia-Romagna, with an increase of 112.91 units (122.27%), indicating a highly dynamic and innovation-prone environment. This can be attributed to a combination of factors, including a solid infrastructure for business support, active regional policies, and an economic fabric that favors collaboration between universities, research centers, and the industrial sector. In the North, other regions like Lombardy and Veneto show significant increases, with Lombardy recording an increase of 81.52 units (64.96%). This reflects the strong industrial concentration and the presence of a well-developed innovation ecosystem that supports SMEs in transforming their production and business processes. Conversely, regions like Molise and Umbria show much more contained growth, with increases of only 2.25 and 12.52 units respectively. These data suggest a lower propensity for innovation that could stem from various limitations, such as lower investments in technology, less developed infrastructure, or a lack of effective regional policies that stimulate innovation. In the South, the situation is varied: Calabria and Puglia show promising increases of 77.23 (83.92%) and 58.50 (66.86%) units, signaling a transforming environment that is beginning to recognize the value of innovation. However, these regions, along with Sicily, which shows a modest increase of 18.81 units (21.65%), could still benefit from greater support to consolidate these positive trends. The regional analysis underscores the importance of innovation support policies, highlighting how regions with proactive programs and an effective support network tend to show better results. Investments in technology, credit facilitation, tax incentives, and training programs for SMEs are key elements that can accelerate the adoption of new processes and technologies. In conclusion, while Northern Italy continues to show a strong propensity for innovation, the South, despite some positive exceptions, remains relatively behind.

Italian Macro-Regions between 2018 and 2023. The analysis of data on the introduction of business process innovations by SMEs in Italian macro-regions from 2018 to 2023 provides significant insights into regional innovation dynamics. These data not only reflect the innovative capacities of businesses in different geographical areas but also underline the impact of regional economic policies and the responsiveness of the entrepreneurial fabric to market and technological changes. The South shows a remarkable growth trajectory in the early years, rising from 88.2 in 2018 to 168.86 in 2021. This increase suggests a period of intense innovative activity, likely stimulated by new regional incentives, investments in innovative startups, and increased collaborations between universities and businesses. However, in 2023, there is a decline to 138.85, which could reflect post-pandemic economic challenges, the end of temporary incentives, or market saturation for certain innovations. Despite this decline, the net positive of 50.65 units and a percentage growth of 57.43% from 2018 indicate robust expansion of innovative capacities in the region. Northern Italy, known for its advanced industrial fabric and density of high-tech SMEs, shows a steady and sustained increase in innovation. Starting from 121.09 in 2018, it reaches 183.06 in 2023, with an absolute variation of 61.97. This 51.18% increase could be attributed to an entrepreneurial environment that continues to invest in research and development, benefiting from a consolidated network of research centers and a regional policy favorable to innovation. The steady growth, even during the pandemic years, highlights the resilience and adaptability of SMEs in the region. The Center shows moderate but consistent growth. The number of innovations remains stable from 2018 to 2020, suggesting possible stagnation or difficulties in adopting new technologies during that period. However, from 2020 to 2023, there is a notable increase from 114.58 to 170.48, with an absolute variation of 55.9 and a percentage increase of 48.79%. This may indicate the effectiveness of new innovation stimulus policies implemented during the period, along with a renewed commitment by businesses to digital transformation and process innovation. The data suggest that despite annual fluctuations and global economic impacts, such as those from the COVID-19 pandemic, Italian SMEs have continued to pursue innovation. The increase in innovation across all three macro-regions reflects notable resilience and adaptability. However, regional differences in growth intensity highlight how various factors, including political support, access to funding, availability of technical skills, and collaboration between the private and academic sectors, can significantly influence the level of innovation.

North-South Divide. Data on the introduction of business process innovations by SMEs in Italian macro-regions from 2018 to 2023 provide a detailed overview of the persistent North-South divide in terms of innovative activity. Starting with a base of 121.09 in 2018, the North shows sustained and significant growth, reaching 183.06 in 2023, with an absolute increase of 61.97 and a percentage change of 51.18%. This suggests that the North benefits from a resilient and dynamic economic environment, supported by strong infrastructure, access to capital, and high interaction between industries and research institutions. In contrast, the South starts from an initial value of 88.2, peaks in 2021, but then sees a reduction, standing at 138.85 in 2023. Despite an impressive percentage growth of 57.43%, the final value lower than the North underscores difficulties in maintaining a consistent pace of innovation, likely reflecting less stable support policies, less developed infrastructure, and limited access to financial and technological resources. The Center, starting from 114.58 and growing moderately to 170.48, shows an absolute increase of 55.9 and a percentage growth of 48.79%. This gradual but stable growth rate could indicate a growing capacity to adapt and respond to innovation policies, although not reaching the peaks of the North. The North-South divide highlighted by the data is not only a reflection of the intrinsic innovative capacities of businesses in the different regions but also of the economic and social context in which they operate. The North,

with its densely populated industrial fabric and synergies between companies and research centers, has created a favorable ecosystem for continuous innovation. In contrast, the South, despite showing signs of vitality, needs greater support to overcome structural and cultural barriers that limit its innovative growth. To bridge this gap, public policies should aim at a more equitable distribution of resources for innovation, incentivizing investments in technological and financial infrastructures in the South and Center. Initiatives such as special innovation zones, tax incentives for innovative startups, and programs for collaboration between universities and industry could be particularly effective. These efforts should be accompanied by a commitment to improve education and training in digital and technological skills across the country. Additionally, creating innovation networks that span the macro-regions could facilitate the transfer of knowledge and resources, mitigating regional disparities and promoting more inclusive and sustainable growth.

Economic Policies. To stimulate process innovation in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), it is crucial for governments to implement a series of targeted and well-coordinated economic policies. The goal is to create a favorable environment that not only facilitates but also incentivizes the adoption of new technologies and process improvements. SMEs, often limited by more restricted financial resources compared to large companies, can greatly benefit from well-structured government support that addresses their specific needs and challenges. An effective strategy begins with the introduction of tax incentives, such as R&D tax credits and tax relief for investments in new technologies. These measures can alleviate the financial burden on SMEs and encourage them to invest in innovations that might otherwise be considered too risky or expensive. Parallel to this, it is essential to provide easier access to credit through specific credit lines for SMEs wishing to modernize their production processes, as well as establishing regional or national funds that offer grants for innovative projects, especially in high-tech sectors. Equally important is the promotion of partnerships between universities and industry. Technology transfer and the commercialization of research can be accelerated through strategic collaborations that allow SMEs to leverage the knowledge and innovations developed in the academic context. Additionally, supporting the formation of clusters and industrial districts can facilitate collaboration between companies, allowing them to benefit from economies of scale and share resources and knowledge. Regarding skills development, governments should offer training and professional development programs focused on the use of new technologies. These programs can help SME workers stay competitive in a rapidly evolving market. At the same time, initiatives to support digitalization can assist SMEs in the digital transformation process, essential for improving the efficiency and effectiveness of business processes. Bureaucratic simplification is another fundamental aspect. Reducing the complexity and time required for managing administrative practices can significantly lower barriers to innovation. Regulations should be reviewed to eliminate those that limit innovation and introduce new laws that favor the adoption of advanced technologies. International expansion is also a critical component. Governments should facilitate SMEs' participation in international trade fairs and exploration of foreign markets, allowing them to access new ideas, technologies, and potential collaborations. Additionally, introducing incentives for sustainable innovations can guide SMEs towards adopting processes that not only improve efficiency but also reduce environmental impact, in line with a growing global demand for sustainable business practices.

Conclusions. The value of business process innovation in Italian regions increased by an average of 52.73% between 2018 and 2023. Looking at the Italian macro-regions, we can see an increase in the

value of business process innovation in the South with +57.24%, in the Center with +48.78%, and in the North with +51.17%. However, we can observe a significant gap between the Center-North, with high levels of business process innovation, and Southern Italy with much lower values.

Declarations

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Appendix

